

Some Applications of Mössbauer Spectroscopy[†]

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Mössbauer spectra of iron-containing inorganic and organometallic compounds provide important information. The products of corrosion of mild steel in dilute saline and acidic medium have been identified and the diffusion constant that gives the rate of the corrosion reaction has been measured. Iron bearing minerals of eastern India are being systematically explored for geochemical information. Radiation damage in steel with iron has also been studied to learn about defects formed in the process

THE Mössbauer effect is the analog of atomic resonance fluorescence in nuclei. It is based on Mössbauer's discovery that the nuclear recoil during gamma emission or absorption could be reduced essentially to zero if the emitting or absorbing nucleus was embedded in a solid. The available energy E is used in nuclear excitation as well as excitation of phonons in the solid. There will be always emission or absorption of gamma rays without phonons being involved. The recoilless zero-phonon line is the Mössbauer line. It is extremely sharp.

Much has been done with the Mössbauer effect using many isotopes¹. The most useful isotope is ^{57}Fe which we too have been using in our work. The relevant data are well known. The 14.4 keV Mössbauer line is due to a transition from a spin 3/2 excited state to the spin 1/2 ground state. The magnetic moments of the ground and excited states are 0.091 and -0.15 nm, respectively. The excited state has a quadrupole moment of 0.21 b.

If the source emitting a sharp Mössbauer line is deliberately moved with a velocity v , the energy of the line is altered by $\Delta E = (v/c) E$. For the 14.4 keV gamma ray of ^{57}Fe a velocity 1 mm s^{-1} is equivalent to $\Delta E = 4.808 \times 10^{-8}$ eV.

A standard Mössbauer apparatus consists of (i) a drive, usually electromechanical, capable of moving the sources, (ii) an absorber which may be cooled when necessary, (iii) a detector, normally a proportional counter, and (iv) the associated electronics including a multichannel analyser. The apparatus we have is an ECIL MBS 35 Mössbauer spectrometer. The multichannel apparatus has been constructed following the design developed at the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (T.I.F.R.). The single channel of MBS 35 spectrometer is used as a window to select the 14.4 keV radiation. The cryostat useful down to liquid nitrogen temperature has been fabricated by us.

Basic data of ^{57}Fe Mössbauer work :

The following facts are necessary for the interpretation and understanding of the work using the Mössbauer isotope ^{57}Fe .

(i) If the absorbing ^{57}Fe nucleus is in a magnetic medium, for instance α -Fe below the Curie temperature, it will feel the enormously high internal field of the magnetic state (~ 330 kOe for α -Fe). The Zeeman splitting of the nuclear levels in such a field will give rise to a six-line absorption pattern (Fig. 1).

(ii) If the absorbing ^{57}Fe nucleus is in a non-magnetic, non-cubic environment, the quadrupole moment of the excited state gives rise to a doublet (Fig. 2). Generally, the quadrupole splitting due to a Fe^{2+} ion is much larger than that due to a Fe^{3+} ion. If the environment is magnetic, the line spacings of the six-finger pattern are not uniform.

(iii) The finite size of the nucleus and the electron density at the nucleus, which is susceptible to changes in the chemical environment, cause a shift of the centroid of the lines. The shift is called the isomer shift and is now measured from the standard sodium nitroprusside absorber.

Some typical results :

We shall describe some of the data collected by us and their interpretation. Without large material preparation and characterisation facilities we mostly use naturally occurring minerals and compounds or study phenomena where sample preparation is trivial. Occasionally we get samples from chemists engaged in synthesis of chemicals.

Chemical information : The valence state Fe^{II} or Fe^{III} can be identified easily by the quadrupole splitting. Very often overlapping narrow doublets are seen, showing the presence of Fe^{III} ions in inequivalent sites; this fact can be combined with structural data usefully. Interesting information

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

Experimental work in Mössbauer spectroscopy was started in the Physics department of Calcutta University in 1980. The field had already been explored for more than twenty years, and any meaningful work was possible only in interdisciplinary areas involving several departments. Professor Sadhan Basu, as Palit Professor of Chemistry and later as Director of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, encouraged the research activities.

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Fig. 1 Mössbauer spectra of sodium nitroprusside and α -Fe (these are required for calibrating the apparatus and the isomer shift measurements).

Fig. 2. Spectrum of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (below, the wide quadrupole separation due to the Fe^{II} ion may be noted). The upper part is the spectrum of an organometallic compound showing overlapping doublets (courtesy: G. Mukherjee, and S. N. Poddar, unpublished).

about the functioning of haemoglobin or organometallic insecticides can be found. Coupled with susceptibility measurements, the spin state of iron can be identified. Magnetic phase transformations have been monitored and the critical indices measured from Mössbauer experiments.

Fig. 2 shows the spectrum of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where the wide quadrupole splitting is typical of the Fe^{II} state. It also shows the spectrum of an organometallic complex with two overlapping doublets. The iron ion appears to be in the Fe^{III} state. The measured isomer shift and quadrupole splitting can be compared, respectively, with detailed theoretical calculations of the s-electron density at the iron nucleus and the electric field gradient at the iron nucleus.

Corrosion: Corrosion^a of iron or rusting is an electrochemical process which occurs in diverse forms under different circumstances^b. One form we have investigated to know the nature and composition of the oxides and oxyhydroxides and the rate of corrosion^c. Rusting is prevented by using inhibitors and surfactants and the change in the rate of corrosion with these can be demonstrated with the Mössbauer effect.

Four oxyhydroxides of iron, α -, β -, γ - and δ - FeOOH as well as two oxides, α - and γ - Fe_2O_3 are known. If the oxygen supply is restricted, the mixed oxide Fe_3O_4 (magnetite) may form.

The Mössbauer spectrum of the corrosion products of a sample of mild steel exposed to 0.1 N

Fig. 3 Spectra of corrosion products^{8,4}. The spectrum at 20 K was taken by S. Mishra and H. G. Devare of T. I. F. R. on the same sample (courtesy : J. Ray).

HCl solution for about five months shows a central doublet with weak satellite lines. The isomer shifts and quadrupole splitting of the central doublet are characteristic of trivalent oxyhydroxides. For more precise identification we note the widely different Néel temperatures T_N of the products: 950 for α -Fe₂O₃, 403 for α -FeOOH, 295 for β -FeOOH and 73 K for γ -FeOOH. The six-finger patterns are expected for the α -form well above the room temperature, for the β -form just below the room temperature and for the γ -form just below the liquid nitrogen temperature.

The situation is complicated by superparamagnetism. Although the temperature is below T_N , the long range order does not set in and the internal field does not manifest itself in the spectrum as long as the sample size is less than a critical size. This critical size turns out to be about 15 to 17 nm and the corrosion products are usually in fine micro-crystallites of size smaller than this critical size. Hence, the spectrum will not have six-finger pattern

but will show only the doublet with quadrupole splitting as it would in a paramagnetic medium. Well below the transition temperature, the internal field builds up sufficiently and the six-finger pattern appears. If α -Fe₂O₃ is formed, its six-line pattern would show up at room temperature. If α -FeOOH is formed, at room temperature the pattern due to the internal field may or may not be seen, the critical size dictating the situation. With β -FeOOH, the internal field can be seen at liquid nitrogen temperature where α -FeOOH will also be seen definitely. For γ -FeOOH, the doublet alone is seen down to liquid nitrogen temperature, but will split at liquid hydrogen or helium temperature. Thus, measurements at room temperature, liquid nitrogen and liquid hydrogen or helium temperature would identify the products easily.

Fig. 3 shows the Mössbauer spectrum of a mild steel sample exposed to 0.1 N HCl solution. The top curve at room temperature shows the central doublet due to γ -FeOOH and weak lines due to α -Fe₂O₃ and α -FeOOH. The identification is done by taking the spectrum of pure α -Fe₂O₃ and α -FeOOH. The middle curve at liquid nitrogen temperature shows no further splitting hence, the β -form is not present. The central doublet splits in the spectrum taken at 20 K, thus showing that it is γ -FeOOH. In this particular case, the amounts of γ -FeOOH, α -Fe₂O₃ and α -FeOOH are 52, 33 and 15%, respectively.

The transmission Mössbauer geometry is not convenient for the study of corrosion rate as the product must form a thick layer and then be scraped off the sample for taking the spectrum. In the initial stages of the reaction the products form a thin layer. The rate is, therefore, better studied by a surface sensitive tool and the electron reemission Mössbauer (ERM) study is more suitable.

The ERM counter has been made at the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay⁵, and the experiment was done by exposing mild steel sample to 0.1 N HCl solution for 5, 10, 20, 30, 60 *etc.* minutes and taking the spectrum. The central doublet due to corrosion product grows steadily while the iron lines disappear. The reaction is an inhomogeneous one at the solution-solid interface and controlled by diffusion. Our data are consistent with the parabolic law⁶ characteristic of the process, that is, the thickness of the corrosion layer grows as $t^{1/2}$, where t is the time of exposure to the corroding agent. The diffusion constant is 1.4×10^{-13} cm² s⁻¹, corresponding to a growth of about 300 nm thickness in one hour.

Unsaturated organic compounds and compounds containing sulphur act as inhibitors. Thiourea is a typical inhibitor. Surfactants usually contain a long aliphatic hydrocarbon chain with one or more polar functional sites, such as NH₂, OH, HSO₃, or COOH. They form lamellar micelles or other aggregates on the metallic surface affecting the cathodic or anodic reaction. We have shown that the slowing down of corrosion can be measured and that there are

Fig. 4. Spectra of a greenshale rock (work with D. Das, M. K. Bose and M. Chakraborti, unpublished). The narrow doublet is due to FeCO_3 , the wider doublet is due to chlorite, and the other lines are of magnetite.

several mechanisms of inhibition. Further studies on the efficiency of inhibitors and surfactants would be interesting.

Study of iron-bearing rocks and minerals in eastern India: By Mössbauer spectroscopy one can determine in a rock the nature and content of the iron compounds—oxide, silicate, sulphate, oxyhydroxide, carbonate or any other form. The most dramatic use of the technique was made on lunar rocks⁷.

The eastern part of India abounds in iron ores. By a systematic study of the ores from a region one can learn a lot about the geophysical and geochemical history of the region. The total iron content can be measured, this depends on the known isotopic abundance of ^{57}Fe , the source strength, sample preparation and thickness and chemical composition. Usually the Mössbauer results on total iron content are lower than those due to chemical analysis, but at least a lower bound on iron content can be found. The ferrous-ferric ratio is much more easily determined and tells us much about the geochemistry of the minerals. Some of the compounds available in pure form exhibit interesting phenomena: siderite FeCO_3 has a metamagnetic transformation at 38 K; the disulphide FeS_2 shows a structural transformation between two forms, pyrite and marcasite; and so on.

Fig. 4 shows the Mössbauer spectrum at room temperature of the middle section of a greenshale rock. The rock had a greenish side exposed to atmosphere; this part was identified as mostly chlorite, hydrated magnesium ferrous aluminosilicate. The middle section had evidence of ferrous carbonate and magnetite. The magnetite lines are easily identified in the Figure. The inner doublet

is due to FeCO_3 , while the strong outer doublet is due to chlorite.

The Mössbauer information of a pure compound, say haematite $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, will always be the same, but where the stoichiometry or the ferrous-ferric ratio can change with geological environment (as in magnetite or ferrites) the spectra differ and provide information. We have seen magnetite spectra with six-lines; then x in $\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ is nearly 0.3.

Radiation damage studies: The study of radiation damage of metal has become important for information required in operating nuclear reactors and space vehicles. Radiation can create point defects, interstitials and dislocations, and occasionally melts the metal which then recrystallises. The potentiality of the technique can be seen from a work of Verbiest and Pattyn⁸. This is an integration of heavy ion physics and Mössbauer spectroscopy at low temperature, radioactive ^{57}Co is directly implanted into aluminium at liquid helium temperature. The sample is annealed at higher temperature to get ^{57}Co at proper sites and then bombarded with aluminium atoms to produce damage. The Mössbauer spectra taken in such samples reveal information on interstitials, clusters and vacancies of various types.

In the Variable Energy Cyclotron Centre (V.E.C.C.) at Calcutta we have been exposing several stacks of stainless steel foils to alpha-beams of energy 30 MeV and taking their Mössbauer spectra. A stack of eight 25μ foils was exposed. The full width at half the maximum (FWHM) has increased by 50% (Fig. 5). Actually two foils got fused in the heat generated in the bombardment and a large part of the broadening is due to increase in

Fig. 5. Broadening of Mössbauer line of iron in steel due to α -bombardment at V.E.C.C. (work with G. Mukhopadhyay *et al.*). Only part of the broadening is due to radiation damage.

thickness. The alpha-particle bombardment destroys the cubic symmetry around the ^{57}Fe nucleus at some sites and the resulting quadrupole splitting broadens the line. Several stacks exposed at V.E.C.C. are being analysed.

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